

2. Dendrogram obtained by UPGMA cluster analysis of the six TNX 1 haplotypes defined from the Indonesian Xoo population showing their phylogenetic relationships.

A total of 125 Xoo isolates—51 from the collection maintained in the Plant Pathology Department, Bogor Research Institute for Food Crops, and 74 collected from several fields near Sukamandi and Kuningan in Aug 1992—were subjected to DNA typing by restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) using the DNA probe TNX1 and by digestion with the restriction enzyme *Pst*I.

RFLP analysis using TNX1 revealed six distinct RFLP profiles or haplotypes (Fig. 1). The phylogenetic relationships among these haplotypes were determined by cluster analysis of similarity coefficients by the unweighted pair-group method, arithmetic mean (UPGMA) using the computer program NTSYS. Four distinct lineages were defined at 95% similarity level (Fig. 2). Lineage A, which accounted for 75% of the isolates, had three variants: A, A-1, and A-2. The majority of isolates (68%) were type A. Type A-1, which was observed in 28% of the isolates, was identical to the predominant TNX1 haplotype observed for race 3 in Central Luzon, Philippines. The third variant, A-2, was a rare type and detected in only two isolates (1%) collected from the same field. The three other haplotypes—B, C, and D—were also rare and detected in only one isolate each.

Only 19 of the isolates analyzed (15%) had *Pst*I-digestible DNA. DNA

from the rest of the isolates was uncut by the enzyme. The *Pst*I restriction patterns observed from the Indonesian Xoo isolates were distinct from those seen from the Philippine Xoo isolates.

The total genetic or haplotypic diversity of the Indonesian Xoo population analyzed was estimated using Nei's haplotypic diversity index and found to be low ($H_T=0.47$), based on TNX1-RFLP data. This low level of genetic diversity could be due to rice crop uniformity and stable climatic conditions (no typhoons). The apparent simplicity of Xoo populations in West Java implies that BB in Indonesia might be easy to manage; however, the sample size

analyzed was not large, the collection was not from widely diverse locations, and the phenotypic variation of the population—in terms of virulence on rice hosts carrying different resistance genes—remains to be analyzed.

Further expansion and analysis of the collection, in terms of geographical and host genotype representation, are needed before we can draw firm conclusions. RFLP analysis of a more geographically diverse collection of isolates obtained from different islands of Indonesia is currently underway. Isolates representing each of the RFLP types or groups will be used for evaluating potential sources of resistance to BB in Indonesia. ■

Use of DNA probes to distinguish mycoplasma-like organisms (MLOs) of yellow dwarf (RYD) and orange leaf (ROL) in rice

K. Nakashima, Tropical Agriculture Research Center, Tsukuba, Japan; P. Q. Cabauatan and H. Koganezawa, IRR

The pathogens causing RYD (common in Asia) and ROL (common in Southeast Asia) cannot be distinguished morphologically from each other, although the diseases are different in terms of symptomatology and vector transmissibility. Their taxonomical relationship has not been clarified.

We cloned *Hind*III-cut fragments of chromosomal and extrachromosomal

DNA from the Tochigi line (Japan) of RYD-MLO. The homology of DNA probes with several lines of RYD-MLO and with a Los Baños line of ROL-MLO was examined by dot-blot hybridization. DNA probes were labeled with horseradish peroxidase using the Amersham enhanced chemoluminescence (ECL) system. The DNA-blotted nylon membranes were hybridized with the probes at 42 °C for 16 h in ECL hybridization solutions. The membranes were washed twice at 42 °C for 20 min in 0.5 × SSC (7.5 mM sodium citrate, 75 mM sodium chloride, pH 7.0) containing 6 M urea and 0.4% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), once at 42 °C for 20 min in 0.01 × SSC-0.1% SDS, and once at 42 °C for 20 min in 0.01 × SSC-

Summary of results from dot hybridization of RYD-MLO DNA probes to DNA preparations.^a

Code	Sample	Origin		Chromosomal probes		Extrachromosomal DNA probes		
		Country	Area	R30	R9	R11	R19	R72
H	Healthy rice			-	-	-	-	-
J	RYD-MLO	Japan	Tochigi	+	+	++	++	++
T	RYD-MLO	Thailand	Chachoengsao	+	+	++	++	++
L	RYD-MLO	Philippines	Luzon	+	+	++	++	++
P	RYD-MLO	Philippines	Palawan	+	+	++	++	++
M	RYD-MLO	Philippines	Mindanao	+	+	w	w	w
O	ROL-MLO	Philippines	Los Baños, Laguna	+	-	-	-	-
	Other MLOs ^b			w	-	-	-	-

^a++ = strong hybridization signal, + = moderate hybridization signal, w = weak hybridization signal, - = no hybridization signal. ^bSugarcane white leaf, sesame phyllody (Thailand), onion yellows, cineraria witches' broom, Japanese hornwort witches' broom, water dropwort yellows, gentian witches' broom, udo dwarf, tsuwabuki witches' broom, pelargonium witches' broom (Japan), peach estem X, and pear decline (USA).

Detection of DNA of RYD- and ROL-MLOs in rice leaves using probes of RYD-MLO, R30, R9, and R11.^a

^aH = healthy, J = Japanese line of RYD, T = Thai RYD, L = Los Baños (Philippines) RYD, P = Palawan (Philippines) RYD, M = Mindanao (Philippines) RYD, and O = Los Baños (Philippines) ROL.

0.1% SDS. Signals were detected with ECL method.

Chromosomal DNA probe R30 (2.8 kb) hybridized with ROL-MLO as well as RYD-MLO. R30 also detected all MLO lines used in the experiments, including sugarcane white leaf, gentian witches' broom, onion yellows, water dropwort yellows, and others. RYD-specific chromosomal DNA probe R9 (3.4 kb) and extrachromosomal DNA probes R11 (2.6 kb), R19 (4.6 kb), and R72 (1.2 kb) hybridized with all of the RYD-MLO lines, but not with ROL-MLO. RYD collected from Mindanao, Philippines, gave weaker signals with extrachromosomal DNA probes than the other RYD lines (see table and figure).

These results indicate that the MLO causing ROL is genetically different from the RYD-MLO. ROL-MLO can now be distinguished from RYD-MLO by using DNA probes from RYD-MLO. ■

Toxin produced by *Sacrocladium oryzae* involved in inducing sheath rot (ShR) symptoms in rice

T. Vasantha Devi and S. S. Gnanamanickam, Center for Advanced Studies in Botany, University of Madras, Madras 600025, India

ShR, caused by the fungal pathogen *S. oryzae*, has become a major production constraint as more densely planted, N-responsive, high-yielding rice cultivars are used in India. Reports conflict on the success of chemical control of ShR.

Association of a toxin with ShR symptoms had not previously been established. Some of our earlier work, however, confirmed reports by Japanese researchers of cerulenin production in culture. We found that artificially applying cerulenin induced rotting of rice sheaths like that induced by *S. oryzae*.

We studied ShR incidence in farmers' fields in Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, and Pondicherry states and obtained 40

isolates of *S. oryzae* from infected tissues and seeds. Isolate No. 22, which came from the most severely ShR-infected field, was the most virulent on TKM9, IR20, and IR50 plants in greenhouse inoculations.

Production of cerulenin by *S. oryzae* isolates was assessed by the inhibition of *Candida albicans KF-1* in potato dextrose agar (PDA) plates in repeated laboratory assays. Virulent isolates produced larger inhibition zones (Fig. 1), and low virulent isolates produced smaller inhibition zones. Most virulent isolate No. 22 produced a 30-mm-diameter zone and least virulent No. 6, a 6-mm-diameter zone. Amending PDA assay plates with lauric and oleic acids at 1-1000 ppm reversed the action of cerulenin-induced inhibition and confirmed the presence of cerulenin, which inhibits fatty acid synthetase.

We generated cerulenin-negative mutants of isolates No. 22 and No. 6 using UV irradiation. The mutants did not inhibit *C. albicans KF-1* or other fungal pathogens of rice including *Pyricularia grisea*, *Helminthosporium oryzae*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, and *Gaumannomyces graminis* var. *oryzae* in

1. *Candida albicans KF-1*-inhibition assay for cerulenin production of *S. oryzae* and control (right).

2. Induction of ShR symptoms (indicated by arrows) by wild-type (a) and no induction by cerulenin-negative mutant (b) isolates of *S. oryzae*.